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Matched dielectric slot waveguide as an all-dielectric terahertz magnetic dipole

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We observe that the modal field distribution of a dielectric slot waveguide closely resembles a magnetic dipole antenna. Such an aperture distribution traditionally demands metals, making it ill-suited to high frequencies due to excessive ohmic loss. By terminating a dielectric slot waveguide with a matched free-space interface, a compact all-dielectric radiating magnetic dipole is realized. In this way, we introduce general-purpose dipole antennas, which have long been a mainstay of RF and microwave ranges, into the realm of light wave photonic integrated circuits. The existence of the desired magnetic dipole aperture distribution is experimentally confirmed in the terahertz range, at ~ 275 GHz, and good matching is evident in the ~ -25 dB reflection level. This is the electrically smallest radiator to ever be incorporated into an all-dielectric waveguiding platform.

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A dipole is defined abstractly as a vector field quantity that is confined along a line segment and oriented parallel thereto and is a very useful tool for thinking in the fields of antennas and electromagnetics [1]. Far from being purely theoretical, it is well-known that an electric dipole can be realized with a simple current-carrying length of wire, to serve as a radiating front-end for RF and microwave-range systems. Conversely, Babinet's principle states that a magnetic dipole is implemented with the inverse structure, i.e., by cutting a slot into a metal plane and attaching an electric current source across the center [2].

Planar metallic slot dipole antennas have found uses in the terahertz range, most notably with resonant tunneling diode oscillators, for which they serve as both a resonant cavity and a radiator [3,4]. However, fields are highly concentrated within the slot, resulting in strong interaction with metals that exhibit increasing Ohmic loss at higher frequencies [5]. The result is an inefficient antenna. Not only that, planar metallic antennas in the terahertz range pose technical challenges as they must generally be "on-chip," i.e., fabricated upon high-index semiconductor substrates to allow for close integration with active components [3,4,6,7]. A thick-substrate chip will lead to substrate modes,

inefficient radiation, and irregular frequency-dependent radiation patterns with numerous sidelobes. This may be addressed by thinning the substrate, but this renders the chip fragile and causes poor front-to-back ratio. The most common solution is therefore to backside-couple a thick chip to a high-index silicon lens that extracts and radiates the terahertz waves [3,8]. The great prevalence of this solution has actually caused a counter-intuitive *lack* of compact *low-gain* terahertz antennas for applications that demand wider field of view, which currently require workarounds [9]. We aim to address this absence.

Dielectric resonator antennas (DRAs) were proposed to mitigate the Ohmic loss of metallic antennas at high frequencies because their resonance is of displacement current, as opposed to conduction current [10,11]. As with the aforementioned metallic slot antennas, DRAs can produce a magnetic-dipole aperture distribution [12] and have been deployed as radiating front-ends above 300 GHz [7]. That said, the dielectric cavity's resonance must generally be excited with metallic waveguides such as planar slotlines or coaxial waveguides, and so Ohmic loss is only partially avoided. It would be preferable to omit metals altogether to further increase operation frequency.

Emerging terahertz all-dielectric integrated circuits [5] enable the direct integration of a terahertz dielectric waveguide with a likewise dielectric antenna, eschewing metals altogether. That said, the majority of antennas of this sort have utilized electrically large integrated optics [13–15], or longitudinally tapered rods [16], and hence are quite far from a compact dipole. Reports of small antennas are far less prevalent, but there is one DRA of note [17]. However, in contrast to a dipole, the cited antenna exhibited a compound, higher-order mode of resonance, and bandwidth was limited by its matching mechanism. The only truly all-dielectric magnetic dipole antennas have so far been metasurfaces [18], which must be excited from free-space due to the absence of a waveguide feed, and hence cannot serve as a radiating front-end for a given system. That said, it is also possible to evanescently couple to a magnetic-dipole cavity resonator [19], which could potentially serve as an all-dielectric radiating front-end, although this is not explored here.

In this work, we present simple and compact magnetic dipole antennas that are wholly free of metals and are integrated directly together with a dielectric waveguide feed. They are therefore

Fig. 1. Illustration of four different magnetic dipoles. (a) Conceptual correspondence between the modal field distribution of a dielectric slot waveguide and a metallic slot antenna, (b) quarter-wave antenna with electrical size at 275 GHz indicated, and (c) “fountain-pen” antenna.

adaptable to arbitrary dielectric waveguide-based photonic integrated circuit platforms across the electromagnetic spectrum. This is achieved by terminating a dielectric waveguide with a short length of dielectric slot waveguide [20] and matching the structure to free-space. This yields a highly compact all-dielectric magnetic-dipole antenna, at just $0.37\lambda_0 \times 0.14\lambda_0 \times 0.18\lambda_0$, and an electrical volume of $<0.01\lambda_0^3$. We confirm the existence of the dipole via correspondence between measured and simulated radiation characteristics. These magnetic dipoles hold potential for terahertz-range scanning near-field microscopy imaging due to the localization of modal fields in the aperture distribution [21], although it is incidentally noted that conventional planar metallic antennas can achieve narrower gaps [4,22] and hence stronger localization. Our antenna may also serve for dense antenna arrays, as a convenient feed for quasi-optics, i.e., to realize high-gain antennas [23], and for synthetic aperture radar [24].

Our innovation hinges upon the specific characteristics of the modal field distribution of a dielectric slot waveguide, or “void nanostructure” [20]. It is noted that guides of this sort have previously been demonstrated in the terahertz range [25], and have been deployed as compact feeds for integrated optics [15,26], as micro-mechanical phase shifters [27], and in our preliminary work, as hollow-waveguide couplers albeit at mm-wave frequencies [28]. To our knowledge, however, the viability of dielectric slot waveguides as a compact radiating antenna has never before been demonstrated at any frequency.

A dielectric slot waveguide confines waves in a low-index gap between two high-index walls [20], as illustrated in Fig. 1(a). The electric field vector is oriented across the narrow gap, reaching from one wall to another, and the magnetic component is parallel to the wall in the cross-sectional plane. We wish to emphasize that these statements are equally true of a metallic slot dipole antenna [2]; the electric field vector is oriented across the metal slot, and the magnetic component extends along it. Thus, our key observation is that the propagating mode in a dielectric slot waveguide corresponds closely to the aperture distribution of the classical metallic-slot magnetic dipole.

A dielectric slot waveguide’s propagating mode is an innate magnetic dipole, and so a magnetic-dipole aperture distribution is produced by simply cleaving the guide in its cross-sectional plane and allowing it to radiate to free-space. However, this sudden termination causes unavoidable index mismatch and undesired reflections. In order to address this, matching is achieved by cancellation of the reflections from the aperture with additional reflections supplied by the input of the slot, which is connected directly to a conventional dielectric waveguide, or channel guide. We exploit two different matching techniques in order to engineer this desired cancellation effect: first, quarter-wave matching [29], and then second, the introduction of an integrated scatterer into the waveguide feed [17]. Both are showcased at 275 GHz, although adaptation to other frequencies is entirely possible, as shown in Supplement 1.

The dielectric waveguide feed is of identical outer dimensions to the slot waveguide, making the characteristic gap of the latter the only difference. A single parameter—gap width—controls the effective modal index of the slot waveguide section [30], which we set equal to the square root of that of the channel-guide feed to fulfill one of the two conditions of quarter-wave matching [29]. The other is that the slot must be a quarter-wave long, and the all-intrinsic-silicon antenna that satisfies both is shown in Fig. 1(b). Dimensions are optimized using full-wave simulations, as detailed in Supplement 1. We wish to highlight the simplicity and generality of our final structure; we need only remove a small rectangle, and a matched all-dielectric dipole antenna is realized.

Despite the simplicity of the quarter-wave antenna, the fact that its slot width is fixed does deprive us of one degree of freedom. In applications that require stronger field localization, such as near-field imaging, a narrower gap is preferable. This would also be a closer approximation of a theoretical infinitesimal-width dipole. We therefore design a second antenna with a $20\ \mu\text{m}$ gap, which is the minimum that is fabricable. This narrower gap is associated with higher effective modal index [30], causing stronger mismatch with free-space. We compensate for this with a circular through-hole scatterer [17] that supplies additional reflections at the input of the slot. The slot length and scatterer dimensions are optimized using full-wave simulations, and the result, shown in Fig. 1(c), is dubbed the “fountain-pen” because of the scatterer’s resemblance to a pen’s ink reservoir.

Full-wave simulations are utilized to visualize aperture distributions. We first consider a truncated dielectric waveguide, with no slot, for comparison to our antennas. As shown in Fig. 2(a), the truncated tip’s field distribution is too wide to be classified as a dipole antenna. However, once the matched slot section is introduced, as shown in Figs. 2(b) and 2(c), the desired magnetic-dipole feature is clearly visible, and so we conclude that the slot section is indeed required to produce this feature. As expected, the dipole is narrower in the case of the “fountain-pen,” and this comparison is illustrated in more detail, with one-dimensional plots of the Poynting vector magnitude in the E -plane, in Fig. 2(d). It is noted that, as this quantity pertains to power flow, this is the truest representation of the radiating portion of the aperture; H -fields that do not overlap therewith are reactive and hence non-radiative. Thus, although the H -field distribution is not significantly narrower than that of the truncated tip, the gap-confined E -fields essentially define a narrow window through which power is transferred to free-space, i.e., an aperture. The H -field vector is parallel to the long edge of

Fig. 2. Simulated field distributions of the aperture distribution evaluated at 1 μm from the aperture. (a)–(c) Truncated guide, the quarter-wave-matched antenna, and the “fountain-pen” antenna, respectively, where scalar E -fields are shown in linear-scale, normalized to the same value, and H -fields as vector plots at the instant at which the center pixel’s y -value is at the apex, and (d) Poynting vector magnitudes in the E -plane.

this window, and so we conclude that the radiating aperture distribution is indeed a magnetic dipole, as intended.

We fabricate all three structures analyzed in Fig. 2 using deep reactive ion etching, in which ions are accelerated from an inductively coupled plasma source into a silicon wafer, achieving etch rates as high as 10 μm/min [31]. Radiation characteristics are probed using a vector network analyzer equipped with 220–330 GHz terahertz extension heads. The terahertz-wave interface of the extension heads is a hollow metallic waveguide, which accesses the 2 cm-long silicon channel waveguide section by tapering the latter over 3 mm to a pointed tip that is inserted directly into the former. This achieves progressive matching and efficient excitation of the fundamental mode of the dielectric guide [5], and ensures the desired polarization. In order to support the silicon structure during probing, it rests upon a thin 3D-printed polymer membrane plinth, as shown in Fig. 3(a).

We evaluate S_{11} in order to appraise matching performance. Given that the interface between the extension head and the silicon guide produces additional, potentially confounding reflections, we employ time-gating to extract the desired portion of the reflection response, and the result is shown in Fig. 3(b). There is reasonable agreement between the simulation and the experiment, and it is clear that, while the truncated

Fig. 3. Experimental characterization. (a) Photograph of the setup, with inset micrograph showing the antenna and a 500-μm scale bar, (b) matching performance compared to a truncated tip, and (c) and (d) normalized E -plane radiation patterns.

tip is poorly matched, both magnetic-dipole antennas exhibit very low reflection, i.e., ~ -25 dB at minimum. It is also noted that this reflection is essentially the only detriment to radiation efficiency, as the material absorption of a high-resistivity intrinsic silicon is negligible at the subwavelength scale [5]. Thus, we estimate radiation efficiency $>99\%$, in contrast to the $<30\%$ radiation efficiency reported for conventional planar metallic on-chip antennas [32]. We also note a degree of frequency-detuning, which we ascribe to fabrication tolerances, as detailed in Supplement 1. In particular, the narrow gap of the “fountain-pen” is sensitive to tolerances, and the minimum reflection is altered because the precise relationship between a scatterer and a slot length is not accurately maintained. Nevertheless, the matching bandwidth, i.e., the span over which $|S_{11}| < -10$ dB, is essentially unchanged at ~ 20 GHz. Future design iterations may also be able to pre-compensate for the detuning effect via subtle adjustment of the mask layout prior to fabrication.

The results in Fig. 3(b) show that the “fountain-pen” is narrower-band, at ~8% relative bandwidth. In comparison, 32% is measured for quarter-wave matching, and this extends to 47% in simulation, making this antenna more broadband than the 30–40% offered by conventional terahertz planar metallic slot dipoles [22], although verification of the full matching bandwidth is beyond the capability of the instrumentation system. Conversely, Fig. 2(d) shows the aperture distributions span 41 μm ($0.04\lambda_0$) and 96 μm ($0.09\lambda_0$). This cross-comparison articulates a clear trade-off between field localization in the E -plane and matching bandwidth; a narrow slot is narrowband. There is also potential to establish a “sliding-scale,” i.e., using smaller scatterers and intermediate-width slots, although this possibility is not explored here.

Radiation patterns are evaluated by collecting terahertz waves with a horn antenna in the far-field and rotating the antenna under test around its termination. As with the reflection response, time-gating is employed to extract the portion of measured S_{21} that corresponds to a single flight between the antenna under test and the receiver. We plot the radiation patterns at the measured center frequency of matching because this is a truer representation of the field pattern emitted by the magnetic-dipole field distribution, but it is noted that the frequencies of simulation and measurement in Figs. 3(c) and 3(d) are slightly detuned with respect to each other as a consequence. Nevertheless, we observe a characteristic single-lobe, wide-beam radiation pattern that closely agrees with simulation. Thus, the fact that measurements of both matching performance and radiation pattern correspond to the simulation in which the magnetic dipole is evident, i.e., in Figs. 2(b) and 2(c), confirms the existence of the desired magnetic dipole. It is also noted that these antennas are more directive than the ideal magnetic-dipole cavity resonators [33] owing to factors including a lack of rotational symmetry and nonzero Poynting vector magnitude at either side of the slot, which subtly enhances the aperture.

We have introduced electrically small port-fed antennas into the purview of light wave technology. Specifically, we developed a simple and versatile magnetic-dipole antenna for arbitrary all-dielectric photonic integration platforms, with no metal in the feeding, matching, or radiation mechanism. This is enabled by the observation of close correspondence between a dielectric slot waveguide’s mode and that of a classical metal slot antenna, combined with reflection-cancellation techniques for efficient radiation. In this way, we engineer a short slot section to simultaneously match and radiate a dipole aperture distribution. The existence of the magnetic dipole is experimentally confirmed, and a trade-off between localization and bandwidth is established. The dipole’s small electrical size and localized field pattern are well-suited to terahertz- and light wave-range applications such as in near-field imaging and as near-field couplers and array antennas, and the broad-beam pattern that it emits will be beneficial for synthetic aperture radar and to illuminate a given optic from a short stand-off distance. Finally, hybrid integration with terahertz active devices [4] will enable handheld systems toward deployment outside of a laboratory environment.

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Data availability. Data underlying the results presented in this paper are not publicly available at this time but may be obtained from the authors upon reasonable request.

Supplemental document. See Supplement 1 for supporting content.

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